

Behaviour theories literature review

Categorisation of the identified constructs

The final database consisted of a list of 2232 constructs. This list of constructs was first divided into constructs that were value-related and constructs that were not. The latter were classified as “all other constructs”. This means that they were part of the behavioural theory, but no relation to values was evident from the name and how it was defined (see below and Table 1 for coding criteria).

After identifying which constructs were value-related and which were not, a deeper analysis of value-related constructs was conducted. This analysis considered broad values, specific values (both as defined in *Chapter 2, section 22*), and a set of considerations labelled as value-adjacent constructs. Value-adjacent constructs are those that are not directly broad or specific values, but in which principles or importance (i.e., broad or specific values) play dominant roles (see Table 1). A codebook was developed based on definitions of value(s) in *section 2.2*. Constructs were identified as value-related when they met one of two criteria:

1. The words used to describe the construct (either in the construct name or in the description of the construct) included any of the terms in Table 1).
2. The construct’s name or description fit with the definition of values in *section 2.2* – i.e., it related to principles, preferences, or priorities. In this case the constructs were categorized as “other value-related constructs” because they were generally uncommon (with one or sometimes two occurrences). They included terms like weights, gains or losses, and reasons.

Table 1. Categories of value-related constructs used in the analysis.

Concept	Relation to value
Attitude(s); attitudinal	Value-adjacent
Belief(s)	Value-adjacent
Cost(s); monetary	Value-adjacent
Desire(s)	Value-adjacent
Drive	Value-adjacent
Evaluation	Specific or value-adjacent
Goal(s)	Broad or specific values
Identity	Value-adjacent
Importance	Specific values
Mixed	Mixed
Moral; Morality	Broad values
Motivation; motivational	Value-adjacent
Need(s)	Value-adjacent
Norm(s); normative	Value-adjacent
Preference(s)	Value-adjacent
Priority(-ies)	Specific values
Rationality	Specific values
Rule(s)	Value-adjacent
Standards	Specific values
Value as principle (includes moral; morality)	Broad values
Value as worth	Specific values
Weight	Specific values

Distinctions between these categories are in some cases fluid. In addition to conceptual distinctions around the “edges” of these categories, it is also important to note that the theories we review define and cluster constructs in diverse ways. The analysis was as systematic as possible, but due to this diversity, results are best understood as approximate representations of the prevalence of various concepts.

The coding practice followed four rules: one primary and three secondary. The primary rule was that a construct was coded to the categories in Table 1 if the construct name or description included the term in Table 2.1. The first secondary rule was that if the construct name included only one of our focal terms, we coded it to that category, even if other terms were listed in the description. The next secondary rule was that we coded constructs as “mixed” under two conditions: the construct name included two focal terms (e.g., “Evaluation in respect to goals,” Self-Regulation Theory (Kanfer and Gaelick 1991)), or the construct name included no focal terms but the description included multiple focal terms. The third specific rule involved the “belief” category. Since the term “belief” frequently referred to beliefs unrelated to values (e.g., beliefs about effectiveness of receiving help, AIDS Risk Reduction Model (Catania et al. 1990)), whether the particular belief construct in the theory was value-related was assessed; only those

that were value-related were included. In addition, because “belief” is the most inexact term in the construct list and was often paired with other items in our list in ways that did not add meaning, the following practice was implemented: whenever belief appeared with another focal concept, it was coded as the other concept. The construct “Normative beliefs,” for instance, was coded only to “norms”.